

Beauty of Magic Squares: 3888-Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 144 - Part 2

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The work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=18690>

Abstract

*This paper presents a systematic construction of **multiple order bordered magic squares** at orders 12, 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 108 and 144. for a full structural summary). Unlike classical block-wise bordered magic squares, which are built as multiples of a single block size, the structures explored here incorporate successive borders drawn from magic squares of **different** orders — specifically orders 3 through 8 — each contributing a distinct structural layer. To bring order 144, order 9 is used twice, and finally the order 18 is applied. The magic squares orders are considered as 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 18 and 18. In some cases, **even-order borders** consist of **equal-sum**, while **odd-order borders** consist of **different-sum** magic squares. In some cases, the even orders are also considered with different magic sums. The combinatorial multiplicity of border types at each level yields a hierarchy of distinct configurations.*

Keywords: magic squares, bordered magic squares, **pandiagonal** magic squares, multiple order borders, combinatorial enumeration, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

A **magic square** of order n is an arrangement of n^2 distinct integers in an $n \times n$ grid such that the sums of each row, each column, and both main diagonals are equal. This common value is called the **magic constant** (or magic sum), usually denoted S . For a magic square containing the consecutive integers $1, 2, \dots, n^2$, the magic constant is

$$S = \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2}. \quad (1)$$

Magic squares have fascinated mathematicians, artists, and philosophers for millennia, appearing in ancient texts. Two constructions are central to the present work.

Definition 1.1 (Bordered magic square). *A magic square is said to be **bordered** if the removal of any outermost border of cells leaves a smaller magic square. All entries are consecutive integers.*

Definition 1.2 (Block-wise bordered magic square). *A magic square is **block-wise bordered** if each border layer is not a single cell wide but is composed of smaller magic squares used as building blocks.*

During past years author [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [17, 18, 19]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [20, 21, 22, 23]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [25, 26, 27, 28, 29]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White's web-site [3].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White's web-site [3] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [11, 12, 3].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [30].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 5 [32].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 7 [34].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 9 [36].
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 11 [38].
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 13 [40].
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 15 [42].
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 17 [44].
- **Nineteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 19 [46].

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [74, 75, 76, 77, 77, 78, 79].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 4 [25, 31].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 6 [26, 33].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 8 [27, 35].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 10 [28, 37].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 12 [29, 39].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 14 [41].
- **Sixteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 16 [43].
- **Eighteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 18 [45].
- **Twenty Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 20 [47].

The advantage in working with even number multiples is that we can work with equal sums blocks of magic squares.

The aim of this work is to bring multiple order **bordered** magic squares of orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 108 and 144. Let see below how it is done.

See below the details of above multiple order bordered magic square.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

1. Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

1. In this case, we have considered two types of magic squares of order 4.

- (a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

- (b) The second is formed by two equal sums magic sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 resulting in a magic square of order 4. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 20

- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

1. In this case, we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 5.

- (a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.

- (b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there are two **equal sums magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner.

- (c) The third is **single-layer bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 30

- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

1. In this case also we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 6.

- (a) The first is normal magic square of order 6.

- (b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

- (c) The third one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 42

- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

1. In this case, we have considered 5 different types of magic squares of order 7.

- (a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.

- (b) The second is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle and 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 .

- (c) The third is a **cornered** magic square of order 7 composed of another **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic squares of order 3 at the upper-left corner. Two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 .

- (d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 with magic square of order 3 in the middle. Also there are four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . This type of magic squares we call as **cyclic-double-layer** magic square of order 7.

(e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 56.

• **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 8.

(a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

(b) The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 8, where there is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal sums in each case.

(c) The third is a **double-layer bordered** magic square with **pandiagonal** with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. It has 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

(d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 with a magic square of order 4 in the middle. This magic square of order 4 is again composed two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The magic square of order 4 also have four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Since it is formed by only **strips** of equal width, we call it a **striped** magic square of order 8.

(e) The fifth one is four equal sums magic squares of order 4, where each magic square of order 4 is formed by two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . Since it is formed by only magic rectangles of equal width it is known as **striped** magic square.

(f) The sixth one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic square of order 72.

• **6th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 18**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18.

(a) The first is composed of two types of 6 magic squares of order 6. One is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. The second type is a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and a **pandigonal** magic square of order 4 in the upper-left corner. These are considered in four corners with four different directions resulting a beautiful symmetric magic square of order 18.

(b) The second is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 18 embedded with four equal sums magic squares of order 8 having **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle of all four.

(c) The third is **cyclic-type** magic square of order 18 composed of four equal sums **bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×12 embedded with a **single-layer bordered** magic squares of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle,

(d) The forth is **triple-layer bordered** magic square of order 18. The external boarder is composed of different sums magic squares of order 3. The internal part is a magic square of order 12 composed of two equal sums **bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×12 .

- (e) The fifth is a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of order 18 **bordered** with four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 14. It is composed two equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×8 and two equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×6 .
- (f) The sixth is again a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of order 18 **bordered** with four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 14. It is composed four equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×10 embedded with **single-layer** magic square of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle.
- **7th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 18**
 1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18.
 - (a) The first magic square of order 18 is composed of four **single-layer bordered** magic rectangles of orders 6×18 , and three 4×18 . The three 4×18 are of equal sums.
 - (b) The second magic square of 18 is composed of one **single-layer bordered** magic rectangles of order 6×18 and 9 equal sums magic rectangles of order 4×6 .
 - (c) The third magic square of order 18 is composed of one **bordered** magic rectangle of order 6×18 and one **bordered** magic rectangle of order 4×18 . There is one more **single-layer bordered** magic rectangle of order 8×10 and one single-layer bordered magic square of order 8.
 - (d) The forth magic rectangles of order 18 is composed of three **single-layer** magic rectangles. Two of them are of equal sums of order 4×18 . The third one is also a **single-layer bordred** of order 10×18 .
 - (e) The fifth magic square of order 18 is composed of two **single-layer bordered** magic rectangles of order 4×18 and 2 of order 4×10 . The internal part is a magic square of order 10. It is composed of **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 10 with four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
 - (f) The sixth magic square of order 18 is very much similar to third. The difference is that here we have two equal sums sinlge-layer magic rectangles of order 4×18 . In the middle there is magic square of order 10 and a **single-layer** magic rectangle of order 8×10 . The magic square of order 10 is also a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 10.

Below summarises the construction levels.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**
 - Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.
- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**
 - In this case we have considered two different types of magic squares of order 4. Combining with magic square of order 12 we have **2-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

- In this case, we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 5. Combining with 3 magic squares of order 20 we have **6-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**
 - In this case also we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 6. Combining with 6 magic squares of order 30 we have **18-different types** of magic squares of order 42.
- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**
 - In this case, we have considered 5-different ways of magic squares of order 7. Combining with 18 magic squares of order 42 we have **90-different types** of magic squares of order 56.
- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares. Combining with 90 magic squares of order 56 we have **540-different types** of magic squares of order 72.
- **6th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 18**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18. Combining with 540 magic squares of order 72 we have $6 \times 540 = 3240$, i.e., **3240-different types** of magic squares of order 108.
- **7th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 18**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18. Combining with 648 magic squares of order 108 we have $6 \times 648 = 3888$, i.e., **3888-different types** of magic squares of order 144.

The total count at each level equals the product of all variant counts up to that level:

$$N_{\text{ord. 144}} = 1(3) \times 2(4) \times 3(5) \times 3(6) \times 5(7) \times 6(8) \times 6(18) \times 6(18) = 19440 \quad (2)$$

More details of last border i.e., 7th border of magic squares of order 18 are given in section below.

2 Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 144

In order to get **bordered magic squares** of order 144, we shall use the following six different types of magic squares of order 18 over the magic square of order 108 as an upper border magic squares resulting in magic squares of order 144.

18	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA		2925						
5	3	314	2	313	318	319	312	8	19	16	324	4	311	18	308	316	15	2925	
20	27	36	301	290	30	31	22	299	296	304	293	25	297	23	34	292	305	2925	
315	298	289	24	35	295	294	303	26	29	21	32	300	28	302	291	33	10	2925	
310	322	11	323	12	7	6	13	317	306	309	1	321	14	307	17	9	320	2925	
41	39	278	38	288	282	275	276	44	54	52	277	40	272	55	283	280	51	2925	
56	63	72	261	66	254	67	257	263	70	260	265	61	268	59	256	58	269	2925	
279	262	253	64	259	71	258	68	62	255	65	60	264	57	266	69	267	46	2925	
274	286	47	287	37	43	50	49	281	271	273	48	285	53	270	42	45	284	2925	
77	90	242	74	252	246	247	240	80	76	88	241	91	239	75	236	244	87	2925	
92	106	108	225	224	102	103	229	227	97	94	221	99	232	95	220	218	233	2925	
243	219	217	100	101	223	222	96	98	228	231	104	226	93	230	105	107	82	2925	
238	235	83	251	73	79	78	85	245	249	237	84	234	86	250	89	81	248	2925	
109	202	210	116	117	113	110	203	118	199	201	196	125	195	204	112	197	198	2925	
206	189	145	137	178	132	146	184	182	194	142	144	191	133	177	140	186	119	2925	
114	187	161	156	152	175	157	174	162	160	167	172	166	170	154	149	138	211	2925	
205	135	164	169	173	150	168	151	163	165	158	153	159	155	171	176	190	120	2925	
214	139	180	188	147	193	179	141	143	131	183	181	134	192	148	185	136	111	2925	
127	123	115	209	208	212	215	122	207	126	124	129	200	130	121	213	128	216	2925	
1	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

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296	30	297	32	26	294	43	283	287	40	281	41	248	78	249	80	74	246	2925	
298	290	36	291	33	27	286	279	278	48	45	39	250	84	81	243	242	75	2925	
25	35	289	34	292	300	37	46	47	277	280	288	73	241	244	82	83	252	2925	
31	295	28	293	299	29	284	42	38	285	44	282	79	247	76	245	251	77	2925	
318	6	321	2	8	320	308	18	14	20	309	306	236	90	237	92	86	234	2925	
324	12	9	315	314	1	310	24	21	303	302	15	238	96	93	231	230	87	2925	
3	313	316	10	11	322	13	301	304	22	23	312	85	229	232	94	95	240	2925	
5	319	4	323	317	7	19	307	311	305	16	17	91	235	88	233	239	89	2925	
270	56	273	54	50	272	260	66	62	261	68	258	224	102	225	104	98	222	2925	
51	60	57	266	267	274	262	72	69	255	254	63	226	108	105	219	218	99	2925	
276	265	268	59	58	49	61	253	256	70	71	264	97	217	220	106	107	228	2925	
53	269	52	271	275	55	67	259	263	64	257	65	103	223	100	221	227	101	2925	
109	202	113	116	117	210	110	203	118	199	201	125	112	195	196	204	197	198	2925	
206	189	145	137	182	133	146	184	177	194	142	144	132	191	178	140	186	119	2925	
114	187	167	157	152	175	154	149	162	170	174	172	160	156	161	166	138	211	2925	
205	135	158	168	173	150	171	176	163	155	151	153	165	169	164	159	190	120	2925	
214	139	180	188	143	192	179	141	148	131	183	181	193	134	147	185	136	111	2925	
127	123	212	209	208	115	215	122	207	126	124	200	213	130	129	121	128	216	2925	
2	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

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5	3	314	2	324	318	319	312	8	18	16	313	4	311	19	308	316	15	2925	
20	36	290	297	27	30	31	22	299	34	301	293	25	292	23	304	296	305	2925	
315	289	35	28	298	295	294	303	26	291	24	32	300	33	302	21	29	10	2925	
310	322	11	323	1	7	6	13	317	307	309	12	321	14	306	17	9	320	2925	
75	72	241	254	256	245	77	82	244	79	44	38	286	288	275	49	277	43	2925	
251	94	87	239	85	236	230	237	92	74	41	270	268	53	274	54	56	284	2925	
76	91	227	103	224	97	99	225	234	249	42	52	67	260	61	262	273	283	2925	
252	235	221	218	108	105	219	104	90	73	47	58	62	261	68	259	267	278	2925	
83	229	102	107	217	220	106	223	96	242	285	60	264	63	258	65	265	40	2925	
70	93	100	222	101	228	226	98	232	255	280	266	257	66	263	64	59	45	2925	
247	233	238	86	240	89	95	88	231	78	279	269	57	272	51	271	55	46	2925	
246	253	84	71	69	80	248	243	81	250	282	287	39	37	50	276	48	281	2925	
109	202	210	116	117	112	110	203	118	199	201	196	125	195	204	113	197	198	2925	
206	189	145	137	133	178	146	184	182	194	142	144	191	132	177	140	186	119	2925	
114	187	170	156	152	175	157	149	162	160	167	172	166	161	154	174	138	211	2925	
205	135	155	169	173	150	168	176	163	165	158	153	159	164	171	151	190	120	2925	
214	139	180	188	192	147	179	141	143	131	183	181	134	193	148	185	136	111	2925	
127	123	115	209	208	213	215	122	207	126	124	129	200	130	121	212	128	216	2925	
5	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

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20	27	36	297	304	30	31	301	299	23	296	293	25	292	22	290	34	305	2925	
315	298	289	28	21	295	294	24	26	302	29	32	300	33	303	35	291	10	2925	
310	322	11	323	1	7	6	13	317	307	309	12	321	14	306	17	9	320	2925	
89	243	237	242	78	77	86	231	235	96	98	238	249	241	75	74	91	245	2925	
232	100	218	109	116	213	208	219	120	224	108	110	211	103	212	115	214	93	2925	
85	119	137	193	196	190	121	197	133	202	191	200	127	138	126	124	206	240	2925	
230	207	189	147	142	148	145	184	140	174	173	150	186	182	179	136	118	95	2925	
97	221	195	181	160	172	164	167	166	155	154	163	168	156	144	130	104	228	2925	
246	223	131	176	165	153	161	158	159	170	171	162	157	169	149	194	102	79	2925	
233	220	122	146	183	177	180	141	185	151	152	175	139	143	178	203	105	92	2925	
252	99	201	132	129	135	204	128	192	123	134	125	198	187	199	188	226	73	2925	
81	111	107	216	209	112	117	106	205	101	217	215	114	222	113	210	225	244	2925	
80	82	88	83	247	248	239	94	90	229	227	87	76	84	250	251	234	236	2925	
41	39	278	275	288	282	283	276	44	54	52	277	40	272	55	38	280	51	2925	
56	254	72	261	63	66	67	265	263	70	260	257	61	256	59	268	58	269	2925	
279	71	253	64	262	259	258	60	62	255	65	68	264	69	266	57	267	46	2925	
274	286	47	50	37	43	42	49	281	271	273	48	285	53	270	287	45	284	2925	
3	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

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20	27	36	297	304	30	31	301	299	23	296	293	25	290	22	292	34	305	2925
315	298	289	28	21	295	294	24	26	302	29	32	300	35	303	33	291	10	2925
310	322	11	323	1	7	6	13	306	307	309	12	321	14	317	17	9	320	2925
79	252	242	77	203	196	198	210	130	128	126	116	114	204	99	232	222	97	2925
241	235	90	84	125	137	190	131	192	145	182	139	184	200	221	215	110	104	2925
244	92	233	81	123	132	191	138	189	140	183	146	181	202	224	112	213	101	2925
78	88	237	247	119	194	133	188	135	186	141	180	143	206	98	108	217	227	2925
80	239	86	245	113	187	136	193	134	179	144	185	142	212	100	219	106	225	2925
249	85	240	76	201	153	174	147	176	161	166	155	168	124	229	105	220	96	2925
82	238	87	243	205	148	175	154	173	156	167	162	165	120	102	218	107	223	2925
74	89	236	251	207	178	149	172	151	170	157	164	159	118	94	109	216	231	2925
250	234	91	75	208	171	152	177	150	163	160	169	158	117	230	214	111	95	2925
248	73	83	246	121	129	127	115	195	197	199	209	211	122	228	93	103	226	2925
41	39	278	288	275	282	283	276	44	54	52	277	40	272	55	38	280	51	2925
56	254	268	261	63	72	67	265	263	70	260	257	61	256	59	58	66	269	2925
279	71	57	64	262	253	258	60	62	255	65	68	264	69	266	267	259	46	2925
274	286	47	37	50	43	42	49	281	271	273	48	285	53	270	287	45	284	2925
4	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

18	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	2925														
5	3	314	19	324	318	319	312	16	18	2	313	4	311	8	308	316	15	2925	
20	27	36	299	304	31	34	301	296	23	297	292	25	290	22	293	30	305	2925	
315	298	289	26	21	294	291	24	29	302	28	33	300	35	303	32	295	10	2925	
310	322	11	306	1	7	6	13	309	307	323	12	321	14	317	17	9	320	2925	
203	125	201	123	208	113	205	119	207	121	79	248	80	247	74	87	243	242	2925	
198	138	135	136	141	191	186	185	188	127	76	98	97	225	231	95	229	249	2925	
128	132	176	146	152	172	154	175	193	197	81	89	223	106	217	104	236	244	2925	
196	192	174	161	156	170	163	151	133	129	250	235	107	214	111	218	90	75	2925	
130	194	147	166	167	157	160	178	131	195	252	233	220	112	213	105	92	73	2925	
126	143	180	155	162	164	169	145	182	199	241	232	101	109	216	224	93	84	2925	
116	181	148	168	165	159	158	177	144	209	237	226	103	215	110	222	99	88	2925	
210	183	150	179	173	153	171	149	142	115	86	91	221	219	108	102	234	239	2925	
114	137	190	189	184	134	139	140	187	211	240	96	228	100	94	230	227	85	2925	
204	200	124	202	117	212	120	206	118	122	83	77	245	78	251	238	82	246	2925	
51	39	278	275	288	282	283	276	55	54	52	277	38	272	40	44	280	41	2925	
269	268	256	67	261	59	66	265	63	72	260	257	263	254	58	61	70	56	2925	
46	57	69	258	64	266	259	60	262	253	65	68	62	71	267	264	255	279	2925	
284	286	47	50	37	43	42	49	270	271	273	48	287	53	285	281	45	274	2925	
6	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18.
 1. The first magic square of order 18 is composed of four **single-layer bordered** magic rectangles of orders 6×18 , and three 4×18 . The three 4×18 are of equal sums.
 2. The second magic square of 18 is composed of one **single-layer bordered** magic rectangles of order 6×18 and 9 equal sums magic rectangles of order 4×6 .
 3. The third magic square of order 18 is composed of one **bordered** magic rectangle of order 6×18 and one **bordered** magic rectangle of order 4×18 . There is one more **single-layer bordered** magic rectangle of order 8×10 and one single-layer bordered magic square of order 8.
 4. The forth magic rectangles of order 18 is composed of three **single-layer** magic rectangles. Two of them are of equal sums of order 4×18 . The third one is also a **single-layer bordred** of order 10×18 .
 5. The fifth magic square of order 18 is composed of two **single-layer bordered** magic rectangles of order 4×18 and 2 of order 4×10 . The internal part is a magic square of order 10. It is composed of **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 10 with four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

6. The sixth magic square of order 18 is very much similar to third. The difference is that here we have two equal sums single-layer magic rectangles of order 4×18 . In the middle there is magic square of order 10 and a **single-layer** magic rectangle of order 8×10 . The magic square of order 10 is also a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 10.

Combining with 3240 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 3240 = 19940$, i.e., **19940-different types** of magic squares of order 108. Since this number is too high, we worked with 648 magic squares of order 108, resulting in 3888 magic square of order 144.

Above there are only few examples, but there are 3888 magic squares of order 144 composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 18 and 18. More details are in an **excel files** attached with the work.

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